

PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTERNATIONAL LABOR MARKET

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***Abstract** This article analyzes the main economic measures to increase the demand for labor in the international labor market, such as the implementation of deep economic reforms aimed at increasing the volume of gross domestic product (GDP).*

***Keywords:** international labor market, labor resources, geographical diversification, unemployment, economic activity, labor market, labor force, labor capacity.*

***Абстракт** В статье анализируются основные экономические меры по увеличению спроса на рабочую силу на международном рынке труда, такие как проведение глубоких экономических реформ, направленных на увеличение объема валового внутреннего продукта (ВВП).*

***Ключевые слова:** международный рынок труда, трудовые ресурсы, географическая диверсификация, безработица, экономическая активность, рынок труда, рабочая сила, производительность труда.*

Since 1919, the International Labor Organization has been maintaining and developing a system of international labor standards aimed at promoting the opportunities for women and men to work in conditions of freedom, equality, security and dignity, in a decent and productive manner. In today's globalized economy, international labor standards are an important component of the international framework for ensuring that the growth of the world economy benefits all.

Among the main economic measures to increase the demand for labor, the leading place is occupied by the implementation of deep economic reforms aimed at

increasing the volume of gross domestic product (GDP). One of the decisive conditions for increasing GDP is increasing labor productivity. This can be achieved by providing modern material, technical and technological facilities for jobs, rational use of working time, improving the ongoing well-being of employees, and conducting rational fiscal and tax policies.

Important economic measures include: creating new jobs in industrial and service enterprises; allocating more state funds for expanding production; improving service delivery and introducing advanced technologies; establishing new partnerships, leases, private and joint ventures; maintaining state orders for key agricultural and industrial products during the transition period; developing small and medium-sized businesses and private entrepreneurs; organizing social work, etc.

Important economic measures include: creating new jobs in industrial and service enterprises; increasing state funding for production expansion; improving service delivery and introducing advanced technologies; establishing new partnerships, leases, private and joint ventures; maintaining state orders for the main products of agricultural and industrial sectors during the transition economy; developing small and medium-sized businesses and private entrepreneurs; organizing social work, etc. Among them, the development of small and medium-sized businesses, which create additional jobs and require minimal investment, and the organization of social work play an important role in increasing the demand for labor. The sources of financing the development of small and medium-sized businesses are the local budget, the Employment Assistance Fund and the Business Fund, as well as investments by private entrepreneurs. It is advisable to provide interest-free or low-interest preferential loans to representatives of small and medium-sized businesses.

Studies show that it is necessary to develop small and medium-sized businesses in the service and personal labor sectors. The value of jobs in these sectors is not high. Therefore, many new jobs can be created. In implementing these

measures, it is necessary, first of all, to use the services of private entrepreneurs. Taking into account the specific natural-ecological, socio-demographic and economically developed features of each, it is necessary to draw up a targeted comprehensive program for the development of private entrepreneurship according to the "top-down" principle. Such a program is designed to increase employment and allow for the correct implementation of measures to stimulate the development of private entrepreneurship. It is necessary to constantly stimulate the development of independent small and medium-sized businesses and private entrepreneurship, including attracting private foreign investments. The flow of such investments can significantly accelerate structural changes in the economy. The development prospects of private entrepreneurs are practically unlimited. In addition, a sufficiently large layer of entrepreneurs has emerged in the republic in terms of their scale and quality. Their support and protection by the state within the framework of laws and government decisions creates opportunities for more effective development of private entrepreneurship.

Further improvement of the system of incentives for women of working age and with many children, adolescents, pensioners and disabled people through the provision of various economic and social benefits and quotas is an integral part of economic measures to increase the demand for labor. Continuously increasing the period of child-rearing (in the future until the child reaches the age of seven) and the amount of benefits provided to them will create an opportunity to voluntarily "withdraw" women with young children from the labor market and sectors of the economy. Due to their heavy involvement in family affairs, they cannot ensure high productivity at work. An important way to reduce the "artificial" unemployment of women with young children is to encourage their real activity in raising children and officially recognize it. To do this, it is necessary to redistribute the funds spent on unemployment benefits from the Employment Support Fund to the Social Insurance Fund and transfer them as social payments to women. See Figure 1.

talent acquisition assistant
stability analysis
sales development representative
customer success analyst
marketing manager growth
talent association partner
sustainability manager
workplace coordinator

Figure 1. Modern professions with growing demand (2018-2023)

Economic incentives for the activities of women with many children can be implemented by increasing the creation of quota jobs in enterprises engaged in the processing and preparation of agricultural products, in social and production infrastructure organizations, and in private farms, and by expanding the scope of home-based work.

The problem of youth unemployment can be solved by improving the orientation of adolescents to the profession in schools and increasing the types of income-generating work. It is necessary to provide preferential loans to those who organize quota jobs for able-bodied pensioners and disabled people and set reduced tax rates on their income. Tax rates that stimulate labor supply are an important group of economic measures. An increase in the income tax rate leads to a decrease in the supply of new jobs for hired employees. At the same time, the interest of highly qualified specialists in additional work weakens. An increase in the tax rate will negatively affect the employment of the majority of the population. Therefore, before implementing such measures, a comprehensive analysis of its consequences is necessary.

The following socio-economic measures leading to a decrease in labor supply are relevant: the development of personal subsidiary farms, personal labor activities and other methods of self-employment; greater use of flexible and non-standard forms of employment; the introduction of market methods of organizing production

and labor; reducing inflation; reducing unemployment; increasing the level of qualification, competitiveness and migration of the unemployed. At the same time, increasing the level of qualification, mobilization, export capacity and social protection of the hired labor force is a component of social measures. Currently, there is a serious need to train highly qualified personnel who meet the requirements of market-based economic management. For this, it is necessary to improve the material, technical and financial support of educational institutions and increase the material benefits, social protection and professional qualifications of professors and teachers.

Studying abroad should be funded, first of all, by enterprises, organizations, and private entrepreneurs that have a demand for highly qualified specialists. This will create favorable conditions that will increase the competitiveness, mobility, and export capabilities of the labor force. These will directly affect the reduction in labor supply.

Wage regulation measures can be viewed as a general economic and social method of influencing the supply and demand for labor. It affects the supply of labor more. Since the amount of wages determines the structure of the sphere of labor application and the scale of efforts to work in several places of work. Therefore, the state, by implementing its established policy in the field of wages, can influence the amount and structure of demand for labor. It regulates all indicators of wages. State intervention can be administrative and economic. Its impact on the duration of working time and the payment of wages per unit of work is usually administrative in nature. In most developed countries, the state regulates the maximum duration of the working week and the minimum wage. Four entities interact in determining the exact amount of wages: the state, trade unions, entrepreneurs and the labor market. Although the state may delegate responsibility for wage setting to trade unions and entrepreneurs, it will actively participate in this process. In market conditions, the state should refrain from administratively setting wage levels. Its amount should be

determined on the basis of an employment contract concluded between employers and employees, with the participation of a trade union representative.

Among the organizational measures, the state policy to increase employment of the population occupies a leading place. It should consist of an integral integration of market mechanisms for supporting the employment of the population and changes in the structure of demand and supply of labor, as well as individuals who have lost their jobs but want to work and are actively looking for other types of activity. In the near future, along with the republican regional and territorial programs, it is necessary to develop targeted comprehensive programs to increase employment of the population in certain sectors. Such programs should reflect the following measures: maintaining and stabilizing employment of workers (especially qualified personnel) in conditions such as change of ownership, privatization, economic insolvency of enterprises and changes in their specialization (providing jobs with funds and quotas); increasing the competitiveness of employees; creating conditions and morale for retraining unemployed persons, obtaining additional professions and specialties; encouraging various forms of self-employment; effective use of the Employment Assistance Fund funds to create non-agricultural jobs (loans, preferential loans); economic incentives for enterprises and firms that organize quota jobs for adolescents, women with many children, able-bodied pensioners and disabled people; expanding the experience of hiring young personnel who have graduated from higher education institutions and have not been able to find work in their specialty on the basis of contracts with employment service organizations, subject to the transfer of funds from the Employment Assistance Fund to their salaries; ensuring the creation of new jobs with investments; developing social infrastructure facilities, etc. In addition, measures to improve cooperation between republican and regional executive bodies on the analysis and forecasting of the labor market and employment of the population, as well as on the exchange of information and methods, and to regulate the employment process, are of an organizational

nature. In particular, interested bodies should develop special forms and indicators for continuous analysis (monitoring) and forecasting of the situation in the regional labor market.

On their basis, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction, in cooperation with the State Committee for Statistics and its regional departments, can develop appropriate measures to regulate employment and prevent acute fluctuations in the labor market, as well as solve the problems of their financing and implementation. Analysis and forecasting of employment and the labor market require improving the work of the organizations of the State Committee for Statistics. Currently, there is a sharp lack of information on the demand for and use of labor in non-state enterprises and organizations, training and retraining of personnel for them, working conditions and wages. At the same time, it is necessary to improve statistical research on such issues as the movement of workplaces in various forms of ownership, changes in labor supply and demand, the state of unemployment, training and retraining of personnel. It is precisely such statistical studies that make it possible to determine the impact of the emergence of new forms of ownership on changes in the employment structure of the population, the development of various areas of labor activity and self-employment, and the balance between supply and demand for labor.

At the same time, it is necessary to improve statistical research on issues such as the movement of jobs in various forms of ownership, changes in labor supply and demand, unemployment, training and retraining of personnel. It is precisely such statistical research, in particular, the emergence of new forms of ownership, that will make it possible to determine the impact of changes in the employment structure of the population, the development of various areas of labor activity and self-employment, and the ratio of demand and supply of labor. In this regard, it is necessary to develop a set of measures to improve statistics in the field of employment and the labor market.

In the near future, the implementation of the concept of labor market development will lead to achieving the necessary balance between labor supply and demand and ensuring rational employment of labor resources.

In order to prevent serious problems from arising, the state constantly pursues a policy of increasing the level of employment of citizens.

First, when frictional and structural types of unemployment increase:

- retrain;
- expand the education system;
- expand information about job vacancies;
- increase investments in labor exchanges.

Secondly, if unemployment becomes cyclical, the state uses budgetary, fiscal, credit and monetary instruments, that is: – spends more money on production to increase employment; – reduces interest rates on loans and creditors to increase the interests of entrepreneurs; – reduces taxes on producers and consumers.

Thirdly, the state pays special attention to the organization and regulation of the labor market: - changes in the population, age and sex ratio; - sectoral and territorial changes in employment; - criteria for attracting additional labor to production; - the volume and composition of production and its growth rate; - the territorial location of the productive forces.

The most important economic measures to reduce unemployment are the creation of small enterprises in the sectors of the economy in accordance with market demand. This should be aimed at increasing the scale of production and services. This can be achieved by increasing labor productivity, improving the material and technical, technological and capital supply of workplaces, creating new non-agricultural labor zones, efficient use of working time, increasing the material benefits of workers, and rational taxation.

The complex of important economic measures includes setting future indicators based on supply and demand for basic agricultural and industrial products,

providing mothers with young children and many children, pensioners, and disabled people with differentiated jobs, increasing their material well-being and improving employment by providing them with various socio-economic benefits.

As a final conclusion, it can be said that the main goal of the development of the labor market in the near future is to increase the demand for labor and reduce its supply in regions with a large supply of labor resources. The implementation of the measures listed in the stages of labor market development will lead to achieving a market balance between the demand for and supply of labor in the near future, ultimately ensuring rational employment of labor resources and sharply reducing unemployment. Brief conclusions The unemployment rate is one of the important indicators of the level of development of the country's economy and the changes taking place in the economy. "Unemployment rate" is understood as the share of the number of unemployed in the economically active population. The unemployment rate in the republic can be calculated by comparing the number of employees registered with employment services to the total number of economically active population. Several factors affect the unemployment rate: low wages, poor working conditions, late payment of wages, job cuts, etc. In the period of stabilization of market economic relations, unemployment is a natural phenomenon. Because the matching of labor supply with demand forms rational employment and forms a level of unemployment that is natural for society. The most important social activities carried out by the labor exchange are training unemployed people in new professions, improving their skills, providing material assistance, and recommending jobs.

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